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Project title: Development of mouse mutant resources for functional analyses of human diseases - Enhancing the translation of research into innovation

D10.1 Characterisation of 5 anti-viral therapeutics in preclinical COVID-19 mouse models

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Table of Contents:

Introduction 1

Call Overview 1

Selected User Projects 4

Outcomes..... 5

User Feedback 6

Feedback from Service Provider: Outlook, Hidden Costs and
Problems 7

Outlook..... 7

Introduction

This report compiles information about the COVID-19 therapeutics pipeline trans-national access (TNA) calls i.e., call overview, selected user projects, service feedback, outcomes and outlook.

The main service providers involved were:

- INSERM-CIPHE
- Institute of Molecular Genetics of the ASCR, v.v.i., Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP)

This TA service is housed in WP10 and is provided by two independent INFRAFRONTIER nodes offering two distinct services – access to a BioSafety Level 3 (BSL3) facility to study respiratory viruses and mouse models to study COVID-19, CIPHE and CCP, respectively. These services are offered routinely to researchers of their institutions, to external clients and / or as partners in large collaborative research projects.

BioSafety Level 3 (BSL3) facilities are an important requirement to work with SARS-CoV-2 virus. All procedures will be performed in the CIPHE BSL-3 facility with approval from the French institutional committees and safety office. The Biosafety Level 3 (BSL3) Containment Facility at CIPHE is a state-of-the-art core facility (400 m²) that is accredited by Agence nationale de sécurité du médicament (ANSM). It consists of (1) an A3 animal house A3 (Agreement number: A 13 014 07) having the capacity to host up to 500 cages of mice infected with respiratory pathogens, (2) a L3 experimental areas and (3) a laboratory for in vitro experiments and bio-imaging area. The specific engineering and containment features of the CIPHE BSL3 allow investigators to work safely with pathogens of category B (according to CDC classification). All animal experiments will be done in accordance with institutional animal care and ethical committees and French and European guidelines for animal care. All the CIPHE BSL3 facility operations are overseen by a dedicated BSL3 manager and Biosecurity/Biosafety officer.

The k18-hACE2 mice were used in this pipeline by default. However, to accommodate the user needs, specialized COVID-19 mouse models from CCP were used. These models have been generated independently in-house. As such, they are equipped with up-to-date tools and have access to animal facilities where genetically modified animals are housed in specific units, their use is registered and reported to authorities and inspections are performed on a regular basis. They have established capabilities to produce genetically-modified animals using a variety of approaches such as ES cell injections and have adopted cutting-edge gene editing technologies such as CRISPR/Cas9. They also have specialized personnel with the required expertise to produce genetically-modified animals using state-of-art technologies.

Call Overview

The INFRAFRONTIER COVID-19 therapeutics pipeline went online on December 15th, 2020. The TA call information can be found at: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/trans-national-access-call-covid-19-therapeutics-pipeline>

The applications were collected online via a Google Form:
<https://forms.gle/fGfRUPLvQRgaUEi87> (now closed)

The call was closed on February 28th, 2021.

Overview of Eligible Applications:

Applications were considered eligible if they were from non-INFRAFRONTIER partners and non-commercial applicants.

Country	Applications
Portugal	1
USA	1
The Netherlands	3
Spain	6
Italy	3
France	5
Norway	1
Germany	1
Total	21

Access units:

The free of charge access unit covered the standard COVID-19 therapeutics pipeline from CIPHE that included clinical monitoring, scoring and viral titration (shown below). Specifically, this access unit includes (1) suitable delivery of preventive therapeutics or vaccines pre-infection or curative therapeutic candidates after infection, (2) infection of COVID-19 mouse models like k18-hACE2 mice with appropriate SARS-CoV-2 virus titers, (3) monitoring of mice for mortality, morbidity and clinical symptoms and (4) determination of viral titers in the lung and brain.

STANDARD Access Unit: Clinical monitoring, scoring and viral load

- Mice monitored daily for morbidity (body weight), mortality (survival) and scored for clinical symptoms (weight loss, eye closure, appearance of fur, posture, and respiration). ●
- Viral titers in the lung and brain of infected mice (PFU, TCID50, qRT-PCR) at day 2 and 5 post infection ●

OPTIONAL: Functional analysis and readouts
Outside TA call on collaborative basis

- Organ histopathological analysis ● ●
- Multiplex assay profiling of cytokines and chemokines in lung and mouse serum ● ●
- High dimensional immuno-phenotyping of target organs (lung, brain..), blood and secondary lymphoid organs: ● ●
- Myeloid panel (32 parameters)
- T cell and T cell activation panel (including $\alpha\beta$, gd, Mait and NKT cells -15 parameters)
- B cell panel (10 parameters)
- Humoral (ELISA, neutralization) and cellular immune responses ●

The following results / samples were sent to the users: monitoring for morbidity and mortality, clinical scoring, qRT-PCR and TCID50 on lung and brain, collection and archiving of serum and lung and brain tissues for histology.

During the call, CCP independently generated the following specialized COVID-19 mouse models:

- 1) Ace2 KO mice: Mice deficient in Ace2.
- 2) Tmprss2 KO mice: Mice deficient in Tmprss2.
- 3) hAce2 mice: hAce2 insertion into mouse Ace2 genomic locus. Resulting model provide physiological expression pattern (driven by endogenous mAce2 promoter), which is significant advantage over previous humanized models (i.e., based on K18 promoter).
- 4) chAce2 mice: Conditional overexpression of hAce2 triggered by Cre recombination. Many tissue-specific models can be generated upon combining with Cre-driver mouse lines.

These models were developed internally, and no costs were incurred to the project. These models were planned to be incorporated into CIPHE's BSL3 pipeline based on user needs. This was not required as the k18-hACE2 mice were sufficient for the selected user projects. The next iteration of this service will include these models to allow users a wider selection of pre-clinical models.

Selected User Projects

Applicant	Institute, Country	Project Scope
Amir Abdollahi	German Cancer Research Center, Germany	Vaccine candidate: Applicant proposed to test a recombinant protein consisting of a tetrameric SARS-Cov2 receptor binding domain (RBD) presented on an endogenous scaffold optimized for adjuvant free mucosal uptake of the applicant's vaccine.
Even Fossum	Oslo University Hospital, Norway	Vaccine candidate: Applicant proposed testing vaccines that are delivered as DNA plasmids which encode RBD fusion-proteins. After intradermal injection of DNA followed by electroporation, transfected cells express and secrete these RBD fusion proteins which subsequently target the DCs.
Francisco Sobrino	CBMSO (CSIC), Spain	Vaccine candidate: Applicant proposed a protection assay against SARS-CoV-2 challenge to be performed using transgenic mice K18-hACE2 (expressing the virus cell receptor in the context of C57BL/6) immunized twice with 0.1 mg of dendrimers.
Jocelyn Laporte	IGBMC, France	Therapeutics candidate: Applicant proposed to test a FDA-approved drug that inhibits dynamin activity for decreasing SARS-CoV-2 cell entry <i>in vivo</i> .
Judith Varner	University of California San Diego, USA	Therapeutics candidate: Applicant proposed to test the potent Phase II investigational PI3Kgamma inhibitor in the mouse model of SARS-CoV-2 infection. These studies will determine whether the drug can be used for the treatment of the lethal inflammatory sequelae in COVID-19 patients.

Outcomes

User	Therapy	Project Status	Collaboration Beyond the TA Call
Francisco Sobrino	Vaccine dendrimere	The study is finalised, the results have been sent	Possible coloboration on T cell responses
Jocelyn Laporte	Anti-viral	The study is finalised, the results have been sent	4 new molecule candidates to be tested in 2022
Judith Varner	Anti-inflammatory	The study is finalised, the results have been sent	Collaboration on histology analysis
Ahmed Abdollahi	Passive immunisation	The study is finalised, the results have been sent	2 new vaccine trials and extensive collaboration in 2022. Publication in preparation.
Fossum Even	Vaccine DNA	The study is finalised, the results on clinical score, mortality and morbidity have been sent. The results on viral load by qRT-PCR and TCID50 will be finalised and sent in January 2022 due to the reglementary closure of BSL3 facility	New vaccine trial in 2022

User Feedback

User	Satisfied with the service?	Willingness to pay a competitive price (non-profit) for the same service	Any publications being prepared?	Feedback Remarks
Francisco Sobrino	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	Interesting call. Extending the possible experiments to more than one variable would increase the interest/outcome. Further support to the INFRAFRONTIER team is also required.
Jocelyn Laporte	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	
Even Fossum	Yes	Yes	Not yet	The INFRAFRONTIER Open Call has provided us with a crucial opportunity to evaluate our covid-19 vaccine in a pre-clinical infection model. In addition, the INFRAFRONTIER team has been of great help in designing the experiments.

Feedback from Service Provider: Outlook, Hidden Costs and Problems

Troubleshooting / Problems

- Sex and age matching of mouse cohorts is time consuming
- In-dept and time-consuming discussions on technical feasibility and daily follow up of results for users. It is difficult to update users on the progress of the experiments every day especially with several pipelines running in parallel.

Hidden costs

- Difficult to standardise all projects, especially as drug administration routes and timelines are different for therapeutic candidates. This introduces cost variability for different projects.

Future and viability of the TA call as an INFRAFRONTIER service

- Nearly all users were interested in future collaborations

Outlook

For this TA call, 7 EU countries and USA sent in eligible applications. In total, 21 applications were received – 15 applications proposed investigating new therapeutic solutions to combat COVID-19 infections and 6 applications aimed at studying new vaccine candidates. Only 5 projects were selected for trans-national access (TA) provision. Among the rejected projects, 6 users were put in contact with the service providers to pursue the proposed projects on a collaborative basis outside the TA call. Initial discussions sounded promising for setting up successful collaboration projects. In addition, there were 9 more registrations of interest. One among them was from an INFRAFRONTIER partner and 2 were from commercial users. These applicants were also brought in contact with the service provider for collaborative or fee-for-service partnerships. As mentioned above, the next iteration of this service will include advanced COVID-19 mouse models which allowing users a wider selection of pre-clinical models for their projects. This would greatly expand the scope of COVID-19 pathological investigations possible and improve their translatability.

In conclusion, **there were a total of 30 interested applicants for 5 TA spots.** This underscores the potential gap in European preclinical services for such COVID-19 therapeutic pipelines as offered by INFRAFRONTIER. With this pilot service and a planned dedicated service, the INFRAFRONTIER consortium aims to fill this gap with state-of-the-art services and resources, capacity building, knowledge exchange and technical skill development in the infection field.